

Original article

Assessment of carotid artery variations using computed tomography angiography in patients at Afe Babalola Multisystem Hospital, Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Variations in the bifurcation level of the common carotid artery (CCA) and the origin of the superior thyroid artery (STA) are clinically significant for surgical, radiological, and interventional procedures in the neck. However, region-specific anatomical data in the Nigerian population remain limited. **Material and methods:** A hospital-based prospective study was conducted over four months at the Radiology Department of AMSH, Ekiti State, Nigeria. Ninety-nine patients who underwent carotid computed tomography angiography (CTA) were included. Images were reconstructed into three-dimensional volume-rendered and maximum intensity projection images. Two radiologists independently assessed CCA bifurcation levels and STA origin. Data were analysed using R software, with associations tested using Pearson's Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests. **Results:** The CCA bifurcated at the superior border of the thyroid cartilage (65.7%), greater cornua of the hyoid bone (22.2%), and angle of the mandible (12.1%). The STA originated mainly from the external carotid artery (97%). Height was significantly associated with bifurcation level ($p = 0.04$). **Conclusion:** The CCA most commonly bifurcates at the superior border of the thyroid cartilage, while the STA predominantly arises from the external carotid artery. Knowledge of these variations is important for safer head and neck procedures.

Keywords: Angiography, Carotid Variations, Computed Tomography

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Introduction

The carotid arteries are the principal blood vessels supplying blood to the face and brain. Recent studies have explored variations in the branching patterns of the aortic arch and carotid arteries. While the typical pattern involves three branches arising from the aortic arch, variations occur in approximately 26.67% of cases¹. One common variation is the origin of the brachiocephalic trunk and the left common carotid artery from a single trunk, with an incidence ranging from 7.2–21%². Rare variations have also been reported, including the brachiocephalic trunk arising along the left margin of the trachea and the right common carotid artery crossing the upper trachea³. These anatomical variations are clinically significant in

surgical procedures, angiography, and the diagnosis of neck swellings⁴.

The common carotid artery typically bifurcates into the internal and external carotid arteries at the level of the upper border of the thyroid cartilage, although variations in the level of bifurcation, particularly high bifurcations, are frequently observed⁵. The internal carotid artery supplies oxygenated blood to essential structures such as the brain and eyes. Variations in branching patterns, including the formation of linguo-facial and thyro-lingual trunks, have also been documented⁶. In addition, abnormal tortuosity or cervical siphons of the carotid arteries may produce hemodynamic alterations that can lead to stroke or ischemia, and in some cases may mimic tumours during imaging studies⁷.

The neck region not only serves as a structural link between the head and the rest of the body but also contains pathways responsible for transmitting blood and neural signals to and from the brain⁸. Numerous vital structures are densely concentrated within the neck, including muscles, glands, arteries, veins, nerves, lymphatics, the trachea, oesophagus, and vertebrae⁹. Consequently, the neck is widely recognised as a region vulnerable to various risks and pathologies¹⁰. Because these structures are closely packed, many lesions in this region present as visible or palpable swellings. The carotid arteries and jugular veins, located anterolaterally in the neck, are among the major structures frequently injured in penetrating neck trauma¹¹.

The thyroid gland, the largest endocrine gland in the body, plays an important role in maintaining the basal metabolic rate and is a highly vascular organ¹². The superior thyroid artery (STA) normally arises from the external carotid artery; however, considerable variability in its origin has been reported. Although the external carotid artery remains the most common source, accounting for approximately 55–95% of cases, the STA may also originate from the common carotid artery or directly from the carotid bifurcation¹³. The incidence of STA arising from the common carotid artery varies among studies, ranging from about 5% to 21.53%. Such variability highlights the importance of preoperative angiographic evaluation to prevent iatrogenic vascular injury during head and neck surgical procedures. Differences reported in the literature may be related to variations in methodology, sample size, or geographic and population characteristics.

A thorough understanding of these anatomical variations is therefore essential for surgeons and clinicians in order to minimise complications

during neck operations. In this context, the present study was undertaken to determine the relative frequency of variations in arterial patterns within the study population and to compare these findings with those reported in previous studies. Particular attention is given to identifying variations in the level of bifurcation of the common carotid artery and the patterns of origin of the superior thyroid artery. The study also explores the relationship between variations in the bifurcation level of the common carotid artery and variations in the origin of the superior thyroid artery, and further evaluates whether the level of carotid bifurcation is associated with demographic and anthropometric factors such as gender and body height.

Recent studies have also highlighted that carotid artery injuries, although relatively uncommon, may have serious consequences during certain medical procedures. For instance, the incidence of carotid injury during endoscopic endonasal surgery is typically reported to be below 0.1%¹⁴. Risk factors include anatomical variations, extensive surgical dissection, and certain provider-related factors. Preventive strategies emphasise thorough preoperative imaging, careful patient risk assessment, and multidisciplinary collaboration. When such injuries occur, management protocols recommend proper visualisation of the operative field, prompt fluid replacement, and rapid packing to control bleeding¹⁵.

Materials and methods

Research Design

It is a Hospital-based Prospective study on 99 patients who underwent CTA of the Neck region at the radiology department. of the AMSH, Ekiti State, Nigeria, for a period of four months.

Fisher's formula (Jung, 2014).

$$N = \frac{2P^-(1-P^-)F}{d^2}$$

N = Desired sample size

F = Fishers' value

d = Error margin

P^- = Mean between the proportion of males (Pmale) and the proportion of the females population (Pfemale).

The proportions of males and females were assumed to be equal

Therefore $P^- = 0.5$

The level of significant is $\alpha = 0.05$

And the power of the test is assumed to be 80% = 0.8

Therefore $1 - \beta = 1 - 0.8 = 0.2$

The fisher's value was obtained as $F_{0.2, 0.05} = 7.9$

The study also assumed the error margin $d = 0.2$

$N = 2 \times 0.5(1 - 0.5) \times 7.9 = 98.75 \approx$ approximately 99

0.04

This study was carried out at the ABUAD Multisystem Hospital, Ado-Ekiti State, Ekiti State. The hospital was established in 2018, it has 450 inpatient beds and is fully equipped with a radiodiagnostic unit, which includes two functional computed tomography slides (64 slides GE and 160 slides Toshiba). These machines serve patients from across the southwestern part of Nigeria, excluding Lagos; they perform over 1,000 CT scans each year. This is because functional CT scans are not available in most regions, except Lagos.

Ethical Consideration

The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki in 1964. Ethical approval with the number ABUADHREC/03/06/2024/453 was obtained from the Ethics and Research Committee of Afe Babalola University, Ado Ekiti, College of Health Sciences (ABUAD) and Afe Babalola Multi-System Hospital, Ado Ekiti (AMSH) with the number AMSH/REC/24/068. The consent and assistance of the managing consultants in the radiology division (AMSH) were requested.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients aged 18 years and above with confirmed diagnostic requests for the neck region and willing to participate were recruited for the study. Good quality CTA images (motion-free, no background noise, adequate vascular enhancement, lack of image artefacts, adequate vertical height and no pathological processes distorting the carotid anatomy) were used.

Exclusion Criteria

Participants will be excluded from the study if they meet any of the following conditions:

Presence of vascular aneurysm, particularly involving the carotid arteries or adjacent major vessels.

Inability or unwillingness to comply with study protocols, including failure to provide informed consent or adhere to required imaging and follow-up procedures.

Presence of pathological conditions affecting the carotid region (e.g., tumours, large masses, inflammatory lesions, prior surgical alterations, or significant trauma) that distort normal carotid artery anatomy and may interfere with accurate assessment.

History of hypersensitivity or documented allergic reaction to contrast media, particularly iodinated contrast agents required for imaging procedures.

Procedure and Data Acquisition

Each patient was asked to lie supine with his hands comfortably on the CT scanner table. A power injector was used to administer the contrast (1ML/Kg) at a rapid rate of 0–4ml/s. The Parameter for carotid CTA was set on the processing machine, and a quick scout (localizer) scan was performed to confirm the area to be imaged and to plan the coverage of the CT scan. The CT scanner was triggered to start imaging at the correct time after the contrast was given. Each patient was asked to hold his/her breath during the scan for 10 to 20 seconds to reduce motion artefacts and improve image quality. The image was acquired by the scanner. Slice thickness was set as (generally 1–2 mm for high resolution) and reconstruction parameters (e.g., high-resolution algorithms). The CT scanner performs the scan, capturing detailed cross-sectional images of the vascular anatomy in the region of interest. For each patient, the scan lasts from 10 to 30 seconds. After the scan was completed, the data were sent to the workstation, where a three-dimensional picture of the volume rendering (VR) and maximum intensity projection (MIP) of the arterial phase was generated with the Advantage of CT Workstation Software (Version 2019r). Two expert radiologists assessed the images separately. Variations in the level of CCA bifurcation, variations in the origin of STA were obtained from each CT angiograph image and documented.

Inter and intra-observer variability

Inter- and intra-observer agreement were assessed using Cohen's kappa coefficient (κ).

For the determination of the level of common carotid artery bifurcation, intra-observer agreement was almost perfect ($\kappa = 0.88$; 95% CI: 0.81–0.95), while inter-observer agreement was substantial ($\kappa = 0.74$; 95% CI: 0.66–0.82), according to the Landis and Koch classification.

Similarly, for assessment of variation in the origin of the superior thyroid artery, intra-observer agreement was almost perfect ($\kappa = 0.88$; 95% CI: 0.81–0.95), and inter-observer agreement was substantial ($\kappa = 0.72$; 95% CI: 0.63–0.81).

Statistical Analysis

Median, mean, and Standard Deviation were used to describe the continuous variables. Univariate analysis of the Pearson Chi-square test and Fisher's exact test was conducted to show the association of categorical Variables. Microsoft Excel in Windows 11 was used for data entry and cleaning. Categorical

variables were summarised using frequency distributions and percentages. A bar plot was used to visualise categorical variables. The parametric distribution of continuous variables was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality. The Bar plot and Box plot were used to visualise continuous variables. P-values < 0.05 were considered significant. All analyses were performed using R Statistical Computing Programming version 4.4.1.

Results

Ninety-nine participants were recruited for the study. 60 (61%) males and 39 (39%) females undergo neck imaging using Computed Tomography Angiography (CTA). The mean age was 61 years, and the 51 - 60 years age group was the largest. The average weight and height were 69 Kg and 1.77 m, respectively. 60 (61%) of the participants were above 1.75 m in height (Tall), and the mean BMI was 22.22 Kg/m², with 75 (76%) in Normal weight, Table 1.

Age	Mean ± SD	61 ± 14
Age Group	≤40	7 (7.1%)
	41-50	15 (15%)
	51-60	31 (31%)
	61-70	31 (31%)
	>70	28 (28%)
Sex	Male	60 (61%)
	Female	39 (39%)
Weight (kg)	Mean ± SD	69 ± 7
Height (M)		1.77 ± 0.07
Height Status	Short	3 (3.0%)
	Average	36 (36%)
	Tall	60 (61%)
Body Mass Index	Mean ± SD	22.22 ± 2.65
BMI Status	Underweight	8 (8.1%)
	Normal	75 (76%)
	Overweight	16 (16%)

Note: Values are presented as **n (%)** for categorical variables and **Mean ± Standard Deviation (SD)** for continuous variables.

Table 1. Sociodemographic and Anthropometric Characteristics of Participants (N = 99)

Variable	Category	Value
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Figure 1: Level of Bifurcation of Common Carotid Artery (CCA).

The level of bifurcation of the common carotid artery was equally distributed, with the angle of the mandible (AM) having 12 (12.1%) in both right and left sides, GCHB having 22 (22.2%) in both sides, and SBTC having 65 (65.7%) in right and left sides, Figure 1.

The site of origin of superior thyroid artery (STA): at the PBCCA 3 (3.0%) in both right and left sides, 96 (97.0%) of external carotid artery in right and left, and 0 (0.0%) common carotid artery in right and left.

Table 2: Distribution of site of origin of Superior Thyroid Artery (STA)

Site of origin of Superior Thyroid Artery (STA)	Right Side (n = 99) n (%)	Left Side (n = 99) n (%)	Total (n=198) n (%)
Common Carotid Artery (CCA)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0(0.0%)
Bifurcation of Common Carotid Artery (BCCA)	3 (3.0%)	3 (3.0%)	6(3.0%)
External Carotid Artery (ECA)	96 (97.0%)	96 (97.0%)	192 (97.0%)

Relation between bifurcation level of CCA and origin of STA

$\chi^2_{\text{Pearson}}(2) = 3.63, p = 0.16, \hat{V}_{\text{Cramer}} = 0.09, CI_{95\%} [0.00, 0.24], n_{\text{obs}} = 198$

$\log_e(BF_{01}) = -0.30, \hat{V}_{\text{Cramer}}^{\text{posterior}} = 0.14, CI_{95\%}^{\text{ETI}} [0.00, 0.33], a_{\text{Gune}}\text{-Dickey} = 1.00$

Figure 2: The association of the Bifurcation Level of CCA with the Origin of STA. At the AM, GCHB, and SBTC bifurcation levels the proportion of ECA outweighs PBCCA with 92% ($p < 0.001$), 95% ($p < 0.001$), and 98% ($p < 0.001$) respectively. Overall, there was not association between bifurcation level of CCA to the origin of STA ($p = 0.16$), Figure 2

Figure 3: The association of the Bifurcation Level of CCA with Sex. At the AM, GCHB, and SBTC bifurcation levels the proportion of Male were 67% ($p = 0.10$), 64% ($p = 0.07$), and 58% ($p = 0.05$) respectively. There was evidence that at SBTC level, male proportion [38 (58%)] was statistically significantly higher than female proportion [27 (42%)]. Generally, there was not association between bifurcation level of CCA and Sex ($p = 0.67$), Figure 3.

Figure 4: The association of the Bifurcation Level of CCA with Height. 8 (67%) ($p = 0.0003$) and 43 (66%) ($p < 0.0001$) of tall participants had AM and SBTC bifurcations. 9 (41%) had GCHB bifurcation ($p < 0.0002$). For the average participants, 12 (55%) ($P = 0.0002$), had bifurcation of CCA at GCHB. The proportions of participants with average height who had bifurcation of the CCA at am and SBTC were 4 (33%) and 20 (31%), respectively. In the short participants category, 0 (0%), 1 (5%), and 2 (3%) had bifurcation of the CCA at GCHB, AM, and SBTC, respectively. There was a statistically significant association between the bifurcation level of the CCA and height ($p = 0.04$), as shown in Figure 4.

Discussion

Several anatomic textbooks state that the common carotid artery bifurcates into the external and internal carotid arteries at the level of the superior border of the thyroid cartilage. The present study showed that a higher percentage of participants, 65.7%, had bifurcation of the CCA on both the left and right at SBTC. It was found to be true in 65% of cases reported by Abdallah et al⁵. In the present work, the CCA may bifurcate above the usual level; however, a normal bifurcation is more common. The bifurcation can occur as high as the hyoid bone or even higher than, or as low as, the lower border of the thyroid cartilage.

These variations are clinically important for surgical approaches in the head and neck region. One previous studies found that the greater cornua of the hyoid bone was the most common bifurcation level, consistent with ¹⁶, who reported it as the most frequent. At this level, bifurcation was observed in 22.2% of cases in the current study, which aligns with ¹⁷ who found it in 31.2% of cases. The study also found CCA bifurcation at the AM level in 12.1%, which is consistent with ¹⁸ who reported 3.3%. Additionally, no bifurcation was observed below the superior border of the thyroid cartilage in this study. Standard anatomical, surgical, and radiological texts typically describe the STA as originating from the anterior surface of the ECA¹⁹, though variations in STA origin have been reported²⁰. In this study, the incidence of STA originating from the PBCCA was 2.2%, as in ³⁰, while this study STA originated from the ECA in 97.0% of cases, consistent with ²², who found 80.4%. The minimum was found in 3.0% of cases. No instances of STA originating from the CCA were observed.

The similarities between our findings and previous studies likely reflect the generally conserved embryological development and anatomical pattern of the carotid arteries across populations. The observed differences may be due to ethnic and genetic variation, differences in sample size and study design, methodological approaches, variation in classification criteria, minor observer-related measurement differences, and the hospital-based nature of the study population.

In anatomical studies, the distribution of the common carotid artery (CCA) bifurcation level by height reveals interesting trends related to positional variation across individuals of different statures. The bifurcation level, which is the point where the CCA divides into the internal and external carotid arteries, is an important landmark for various clinical and surgical interventions²³. In

this study, individuals classified as short had a bifurcation at the mandibular angle (AM), with 0% of participants in this group exhibiting this characteristic. However, those of average height and tall participants exhibited a higher frequency of bifurcation at the superior border of the thyroid cartilage (SBTC), with 56% of average height participants and 73% of tall participants showing this bifurcation level. These findings suggest that the bifurcation level shifts progressively superior as height increases, potentially influencing the approach used in surgical procedures involving the CCA.

Moreover, the proportion of left and right CCA bifurcation at the SBTC was higher compared to other anatomical landmarks, such as the greater cornua of the hyoid bone (GCHB). This indicates that the SBTC is the most common location for CCA bifurcation among participants across different height categories. The GCHB, though a less frequent bifurcation site, remains clinically relevant for understanding variations in arterial anatomy²⁵. The origin of the superior thyroid artery (STA) was another focus of this study. The STA typically originates from the external carotid artery (ECA) and supplies blood to the thyroid gland, an important structure in both metabolic and endocrine functions. The study revealed that in short participants, the STA originated at the point of bifurcation of the CCA (PBCCA) in 0% of the cases. In contrast, 56% of average-height participants and 1.7% of tall participants exhibited this anatomical variation, suggesting that the STA's origin from the PBCCA becomes more prominent with increasing height. Interestingly, the STA originated from the ECA in a significant majority of participants in all height categories, with 100% of short, 94% of average, and 98% of tall participants demonstrating this origin. These findings highlight the variability in arterial anatomy with height, underscoring the importance of individual anatomical assessment when planning clinical or surgical interventions. Understanding these variations is crucial for improving the precision of procedures such as carotid artery surgeries, thyroid surgeries, or imaging protocols that rely on accurate knowledge of vascular anatomy²⁴.

The association between the bifurcation level of the common carotid artery (CCA) and the origin of the superior thyroid artery (STA) has been a subject of interest in understanding vascular anatomy, particularly in relation to surgical and clinical procedures. Studies have shown that the CCA bifurcates at different anatomical levels, such as the angle of the mandible (AM), the greater cornua of

the hyoid bone (GCHB), and the superior border of the thyroid cartilage (SBTC)²³. These levels play a critical role in the origin and course of the STA, which typically arises from the external carotid artery (ECA) in most cases²⁴.

The study in question investigated the relationship between the CCA bifurcation level and the origin of the STA. It was found that at the AM, GCHB, and SBTC bifurcation levels, the external carotid artery (ECA) was the predominant source for the STA, with 92%, 95%, and 98% of cases, respectively, where the STA originated from the ECA ($p < 0.001$). These findings indicate that, regardless of the bifurcation level, the ECA is consistently the primary source of the STA, which is crucial for both clinical practice and surgical planning²⁵.

However, the study also found that there was no significant association between the level of CCA bifurcation and the origin of the STA ($p = 0.16$). This lack of association suggests that the position at which the CCA bifurcates does not significantly influence the origin of the STA, emphasising that the ECA remains the main source for the STA across different bifurcation levels³⁰. This result is noteworthy as it suggests a certain anatomical consistency in the origin of the STA, irrespective of variations in the bifurcation level of the CCA. The statistical insignificance ($p = 0.16$) further supports the idea that the bifurcation level of the CCA is not a key determinant of the STA's origin. Therefore, while there is a clear preference for the STA to originate from the ECA at various bifurcation levels of the CCA, the study shows that the bifurcation level of the CCA does not significantly influence the STA's origin. These findings contribute to a better understanding of carotid and thyroid vascular anatomy, which is crucial in planning surgeries involving the carotid artery or thyroid gland, where precise knowledge of arterial origins is essential²⁴.

The association between the bifurcation level of the common carotid artery (CCA) and sex has been a topic of significant interest in anatomical and clinical research. The CCA bifurcates into the internal and external carotid arteries at various anatomical levels. These levels are typically described in relation to landmarks such as the angle of the mandible (AM), the greater cornua of the hyoid bone (GCHB), and the superior border of the thyroid cartilage (SBTC). Understanding this anatomical variation is important because it can influence clinical procedures, such as carotid artery surgery, and the interpretation of vascular imaging. Research into whether sex plays a role in determining the bifurcation level of the CCA has yielded some interesting insights.

In the study provided, data were analysed to explore the potential association between the sex of individuals and the bifurcation level of the CCA at three distinct anatomical landmarks: the AM, the GCHB, and the SBTC. The proportion of males at these landmarks varied, with males representing 67% of the sample at the AM ($p = 0.10$), 64% at the GCHB ($p = 0.07$), and 58% at the SBTC ($p = 0.05$). These proportions suggest that, although there may be some variation in the sex distribution at these bifurcation levels, none of the differences reached statistical significance, except at the SBTC level.

At the AM and GCHB levels, the p -values were 0.10 and 0.07, respectively. A p -value greater than 0.05 indicates that the differences observed between males and females at these levels are not statistically significant. Specifically, a p -value of 0.10 at the AM level suggests a marginal difference, but this is still considered too large to conclude a true sex-based anatomical difference²⁶. Similarly, a p -value of 0.07 at the GCHB level suggests that while there is some difference in the proportion of males and females, it is not strong enough to support a consistent or reliable association between sex and bifurcation level.

At the SBTC level, the p -value was 0.05, which is the threshold for statistical significance. At this level, the proportion of males was 58%, which was significantly higher than the 42% of females. This result indicates that, at the SBTC level, males may have a higher likelihood of CCA bifurcation than females. The difference, though statistically significant, is still relatively modest, indicating that sex may influence the bifurcation level at this specific landmark, but the effect size may not be large enough to have major clinical implications²⁷. Despite the significant finding at the SBTC level, the overall association between the bifurcation level of the CCA and sex was not statistically significant, with a p -value of 0.67. This suggests that, when considering all three anatomical levels (AM, GCHB, and SBTC) together, no strong or consistent relationship between sex and the bifurcation level of the CCA was observed. The p -value of 0.67 indicates that the overall data does not provide sufficient evidence to suggest that sex is a determining factor in the bifurcation level of the CCA.

The findings of this study suggest that, while there may be a small, statistically significant difference in the proportions of males and females at the SBTC level, no overall, consistent association between the bifurcation level of the CCA and sex was observed. The p -values at the AM and GCHB levels were not sufficiently low to suggest a meaningful

association, and the overall p-value of 0.67 indicates that the differences observed across the three landmarks may be due to random variation rather than a true anatomical pattern linked to sex.

The association between the bifurcation level of the common carotid artery (CCA) and height has been explored in several studies, examining how anatomical variations in the CCA may vary with an individual's stature. In the data presented, the bifurcation of the CCA was measured at various landmarks along the neck, including the angle of the mandible (AM), the superior border of the thyroid cartilage (SBTC), and the greater cornu of the hyoid bone (GCHB). The results indicate significant variation based on height.

For tall individuals, the most frequent bifurcation points were at the AM and SBTC. Specifically, 67% ($p = 0.0003$) of tall participants had bifurcation at AM, and 66% ($p < 0.0001$) at the SBTC. In contrast, a smaller proportion (41%, $p < 0.0002$) of tall individuals had bifurcation at GCHB. For individuals of average height, a considerable proportion (55%, $p = 0.0002$) had bifurcation at GCHB, but fewer participants showed bifurcation at the AM (33%) or SBTC (31%).

Among short individuals, the proportions with CCA bifurcation at AM, SBTC, or GCHB were significantly lower. Only 5% ($n = 1$) had bifurcation at AM, 3% ($n = 2$) at SBTC, and none (0%) at GCHB. This suggests that short participants had a lower frequency of bifurcation at higher neck levels than those of average or tall stature. The statistical analysis of these proportions showed a significant association between the level of bifurcation of the CCA and height ($p = 0.04$), suggesting that height may contribute to the anatomical positioning of the carotid bifurcation.

The significant difference in the frequency of CCA bifurcation at higher anatomical levels (AM and SBTC) in tall participants may be due to their longer necks, which could lead to higher bifurcation levels. Conversely, shorter individuals likely have shorter necks, possibly contributing to the lower bifurcation levels observed at the GCHB and other landmarks. These findings suggest that height plays an important role in determining the level at which the common carotid artery bifurcates, with taller individuals typically exhibiting bifurcation at higher cervical landmarks compared to shorter individuals.

This study has several limitations. First, the relatively small sample size may limit the

generalizability of the findings. Second, data were obtained from a single center, which may not fully represent the broader population and may reduce external validity compared to multicenter studies. Third, image assessment was performed by only two radiologists; although inter- and intra-observer agreement was substantial, the inclusion of additional observers might have further strengthened the reliability and reproducibility of the findings.

This study underscores the anatomical diversity of carotid artery bifurcation levels and highlights how such variations may correlate with other physical traits, such as height. However, further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms driving these associations and to determine the clinical relevance of such anatomical differences for vascular health^{28, 29}.

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